

MEDIA LITERACY AND THE GRAMMATICAL PROFICIENCY OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Students' ability to access, analyze, evaluate, create and act on media generates the promotion of grammatical proficiency among students. In the educational trend today which requires modular distance learning, media literacy is one of the visible solutions to improve the learners' grammatical competence. Herewith, the study utilized descriptive correlational design. Fifty-two (52) Grade 9 students and thirty-eight (38) Grade 10 students of Rosario Quesada Memorial National High School were purposively chosen to answer the 50-item perception-based survey on media literacy and the 40-item multiple-choice type of test which was developed and applied to determine the respondent's grammatical proficiency. Statistical treatment utilized in the study was mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages, and Pearson product-moment correlation. The result showed that most of the media literacy competencies have a prevailing impact on respondents' grammatical proficiency in most of its indicators as supported by the evidences. The study also indicated that the respondents used frequently the digital / new media and broadcast media compared to printed media. Considering the significant effect of media literacy to the students' grammatical proficiency, the use of media especially the digital / new media may be advised to be included in the teaching-learning process. School administrators and teachers must conduct in-depth training on media literacy to create assessments and activities for the students to enhance their grammatical competencies. For further studies, various skills such as listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing which requires grammatical structure can be considered to support the study.

Keywords: language, media literacy, grammatical proficiency, digital/new media